

WHAT ARE THE RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN UZBEKISTAN'S TOURISM SECTOR IN THE BEGINNING OF 2024, AND HOW DO THEY CONTRIBUTE TO THE COUNTRY'S EFFORTS TO ENHANCE ITS POSITION AS A GLOBAL TOURIST DESTINATION?

Uktamov Mironshokh Utkurovich

Head of School of Tourism and Hospitality, MDIST

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11369698>

Annotation. *This paper explores the recent developments in Uzbekistan's tourism sector, focusing on initiatives, partnerships, and trends that have shaped the industry in the first quarter of 2024. By examining a range of sources, the study investigates the introduction of new flight routes, bilateral agreements, infrastructure projects, and promotional efforts aimed at enhancing Uzbekistan's position as a global tourist destination. The findings provide valuable insights into the current state of Uzbekistan's tourism industry and its potential for future growth and development.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, tourism sector, first quarter of 2024, initiatives, partnerships, trends, flight routes, bilateral agreements, infrastructure projects, promotional campaigns, socio-economic development, cultural exchange, international visitors, growth opportunities.*

Introduction

Tourism is a crucial driver of economic growth and cultural exchange for nations around the world. In Uzbekistan, a country renowned for its historical landmarks, cultural heritage, and natural beauty, tourism holds immense potential as a catalyst for socio-economic development. The beginning face of 2024 has witnessed significant advancements in Uzbekistan's tourism sector, marked by the introduction of new flight routes, bilateral agreements, infrastructure projects, and promotional campaigns aimed at attracting international visitors and facilitating outbound travel for Uzbek citizens. It can also be noted that the country has numerous achievement for only beginning of the new year. Namely, Shakhrisabz was awarded the tourism capital of the Economic Cooperation Organization in 2024. Additionally, according to information on passenger traffic of Eurasian airports provided by “European Council of Airports” (ACI Europe), Samarkand airport ranked third in its class (from 100 thousand to 1 million passengers per year). Moreover, another Hilton brand hotel has opened in the Samarkand region, and 20-storey hotel, located in the Silk Road Samarkand tourist center, has become one more hotel owned by one of the leading brands in the hospitality industry, Hilton. What’s more, the website of the large British TV channel BBC called Samarkand “the new glittering jewel” of Central Asia. Hence, in January-March 2024, 1,519.3 thousand foreign citizens entered the Republic of Uzbekistan for tourism purposes. Compared to the corresponding period last year, their number increased by 31.7 thousand people or 2.1 %. This study aims to analyze these developments and their implications for Uzbekistan's tourism industry, with a focus on identifying key trends and opportunities for future growth.

Discussion

From the beginning of 2024, Uzbekistan has undertaken various initiatives to bolster its tourism sector and attract visitors from around the world. One notable development is the launch of new flight routes connecting Uzbekistan with key destinations. For instance, Centrum Air

commenced flights between Tashkent and Tbilisi, while Georgian Wings introduced regular flights from Tbilisi to Tashkent, enhancing connectivity between Uzbekistan and the Caucasus region. Additionally, Qanot Sharq Airlines initiated regular flights between Bukhara and Jeddah, catering to religious tourism and facilitating travel for pilgrims. On March 21st, Air Samarkand airline launched its first regular flight from the Pearl of the East, the city of Samarkand, to Istanbul and future plans include expanding regular flights to Tbilisi, Dubai, Jeddah, and various cities in Turkey. Starting from March, at the Islam Karimov Tashkent International Airport, the first direct flight of the Polish airline “LOT Polish Airlines” on the Warsaw-Tashkent-Warsaw route was welcomed.

Furthermore, Uzbekistan has actively pursued bilateral agreements to facilitate travel and enhance cooperation in the tourism sector. Agreements with countries such as Qatar and Kazakhstan have resulted in visa-free travel arrangements and extended stay durations for Uzbek citizens, promoting tourism exchanges and fostering closer diplomatic ties. Uzbekistan has taken an important step with Italy in developing its tourism potential by launching the “The Samarkand Express” tourist train as part of the 25th jubilee session of the UN World Tourism Organization General Assembly held in Samarkand last year. Moreover, Uzbekistan's participation in international tourism exhibitions and promotional events in cities like Vienna, London, and Moscow has showcased the country's tourism potential and attracted global attention.

Investments in infrastructure and the development of tourist facilities have also been prioritized in Uzbekistan. Efforts to develop mountain tourism in the Samarkand region and establish tourist centers and shopping areas aim to enhance visitor experiences and diversify tourism offerings. Additionally, the declaration of 2027 as the International Year of Sustainable and Viable Tourism underscores Uzbekistan's commitment to promoting responsible tourism practices and environmental conservation. Besides, USAID announced that it marks the beginning of a five-year journey towards enhancing the competitiveness of small and medium enterprises across four key sectors: information and communications technology (ICT), tourism, textiles, and the green economy.

The tourism industry has made a number of efforts to support the promotion of the country's tourism industry abroad. On the channel "TRT Avaz", one of the leading Turkish media, a television broadcast was shown dedicated to the tourist potential of the Fergana Valley; the famous reality show by Pavel Volya, filmed at the Silk Road Samarkand complex, will be shown on the Russian TV channel TNT; the website of the large British TV channel BBC called Samarkand “the new glittering jewel” of Central Asia; the American television company CNN published a video entitled “60 Second Economy Uzbekistan”; Tourism Committee invited an Iranian blogger Hubert Sepidnam, known to the world as “mr.taster”, to make a film about the possibilities of gastronomic tourism in a number of regions of Uzbekistan, in particular, Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Khorezm regions and the city of Tashkent; the agreement between Tourism Committee and the European company "Voyage Prive" has been achieved to organize a marketing and PR campaign in Europe to to increase awareness of Uzbekistan in European countries, by attracting leading bloggers and media to promote tourism in Uzbekistan in social networks.

Results

The results includes the list of aforementioned projects:

- Introduction of new flight routes between Tashkent and Tbilisi, Bukhara and Jeddah, and Tbilisi and Tashkent, Bukhara and Jeddah, Warsaw-Tashkent-Warsaw.

- Bilateral agreements with Qatar and Kazakhstan facilitating visa-free travel and extended stay durations for Uzbek citizens, mutual agreement with Italy to launch “The Samarkand Express” railway.

- Participation in international tourism exhibitions and promotional events in Vienna, London, and Moscow, the world known channels, such as CNN, BBC, TNT are promoting tourism potentials of the country.

- Investments in infrastructure and the development of tourist facilities, including mountain tourism in the Samarkand region, USAID is investing on tourism businesses for upcoming five years.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the developments in Uzbekistan's tourism sector in 2024 reflect the country's efforts to position itself as a leading tourist destination on the global stage. Through the introduction of new flight routes, bilateral agreements, infrastructure projects, and promotional activities, Uzbekistan has sought to enhance connectivity, attract international visitors, and provide enriching experiences for tourists. Looking ahead, continued investment in tourism infrastructure, sustainable development practices, and promotional efforts will be crucial for sustaining the momentum and unlocking the full potential of Uzbekistan's tourism industry. By leveraging its rich cultural heritage, natural attractions, and strategic partnerships, Uzbekistan can further solidify its position as a premier destination for travelers seeking authentic and memorable experiences.

REFERENCES

1. Uzbekistan National News Agency. (2024, April 20). O‘zbekiston Respublikasiga turistik maqsadlarda kelgan chet el fuqarolari necha nafarni tashkil etdi? [How many foreigners visited the Republic of Uzbekistan for tourist purposes?]. Retrieved from <https://stat.uz/en/press-center/news-of-committee/53535-o-zbekiston-respublikasiga-turistik-maqsadlarda-kelgan-chet-el-fuqarolari-necha-nafarni-tashkil-etdi-3#:~:text=STATISTICS%20AGENCY&text=In%20January%2DMarch%202024%2C%201%2C519.3,31.7%20thousand%20people%20or%202.1%20%25>.
2. Tour Central Asia. (n.d.). Uzbekistan Tourism Industry Statistics. Retrieved from <https://tourcentralasia.com/uzbekistan/uzbekistan-tourism-industry-statistics/>
3. U.S. Department of Commerce. (n.d.). Uzbekistan: Travel and Tourism. Retrieved from <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/uzbekistan-travel-and-tourism>
4. Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA). (n.d.). A Study on the Promotion of Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved from <https://openjicareport.jica.go.jp/pdf/12363974.pdf>
5. The World Bank. (n.d.). Uzbekistan Overview. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/uzbekistan/overview>
6. State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Tourism Development. (n.d.). Uzbekistan Tourism. Retrieved from <https://uzbektourism.uz/en>